

Obstacle Avoidance using Dynamic Movement Primitives and Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Learning-based motion planning can quickly generate near-optimal trajectories. However, it often requires either large training datasets or costly collection of human demonstrations. This work proposes an alternative approach that quickly generates smooth, near-optimal collision-free 3D Cartesian trajectories from a single artificial demonstration. The demonstration is encoded as a Dynamic Movement Primitive (DMP) and iteratively reshaped using policy-based reinforcement learning guided by model-specific cost designs, resulting in a diverse trajectory dataset for varying obstacle configurations. This dataset is used to train a neural network that takes as inputs the task parameters describing the obstacle dimensions and location, derived automatically from a point cloud, and outputs the DMP parameters that generate the trajectory. The approach is validated in simulation and real-robot experiments, outperforming a RRT-Connect baseline and achieving comparable performance to the CHOMP planner, while supporting multi-modal trajectory generation for different obstacle geometries and end-effector dimensions. Videos and the implementation code are available at <https://github.com/DominikUrbaniak/obst-avoid-dmp-pi2>.

Index Terms—dynamic movement primitives, learning from demonstration, motion planning, obstacle avoidance, reinforcement learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

A motion planner for autonomous robotic manipulation should be able to quickly generate smooth optimal trajectories in different scenarios [1]. Sampling-based motion planners often struggle to quickly find near-optimal trajectories due to frequent online resampling [2], [3]. Learning-based methods shift the major computational effort to offline training, significantly reducing the time to find near-optimal solutions online [4], [5]. More data-efficient learning-based approaches use movement primitives to quickly reproduce and generalize human demonstrations [6]–[11]. However, generalization capabilities, smoothness, and optimality depend on the number and quality of the human demonstrations, which are expensive to generate. In this work, we address these limitations by using only a single artificial demonstration, which is automatically adjusted to avoid evolving obstacle configurations, generating a dataset of optimal obstacle avoidance trajectories for

Fig. 1. System overview including steps 1) to 4) shown as colored blocks, and four example models and applications.

different scenarios. After mapping the dataset to a small neural network, a near-optimal trajectory can be quickly generated in an unseen scenario. Trajectory smoothness is facilitated by the minimum-jerk demonstration and acceleration and jerk penalties during the dataset generation. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the proposed system that efficiently learns trajectory distributions offline, and automatically retrieves a suitable trajectory online: first, the demonstration $x_D(t)$ is encoded as a Dynamic Movement Primitive (DMP) [12], [13] (block 1), offering inherent generalization to different start and goal positions, as well as rotations and scales. During the offline training, a trajectory dataset \mathcal{D} is generated by iteratively perturbing the initial demonstration based on cost functions S , using Policy Improvement with Path Integrals (PI²) [14], a policy-based Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm (block 2). At each iteration, the cost functions define the optimal collision-free trajectory for a unique obstacle configuration, which are described by up to three task parameters \mathcal{T} in two or three dimensional Cartesian space. The dataset is mapped to a neural network (NN) model

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\mathcal{M} , where the number of task parameters n and Cartesian dimensions d are represented as $nP-dD$ (block 3). Online, the task parameters are automatically derived from a point cloud and used to infer DMP parameters θ that allow to quickly generate a near-optimal collision-free trajectory $\mathbf{x}(t)$ in a new scenario (block 4). This methodology allows learning different models for varying avoidance applications. The main contributions of this work comprise:

- A cost-function driven methodology for fast, smooth and near-optimal trajectory generation from different task parameters, after offline training using PI^2 for generating the dataset, including an automatic derivation of the task parameters from a point cloud.
- Obstacle avoidance with three continuous task parameters that can consider different obstacle configurations and end-effector dimensions, and find multi-modal solutions.
- A comprehensive experimental evaluation, including comparisons with CHOMP and RRT-Connect planners and a linear baseline in terms of success rate, computation time, execution time, trajectory length and smoothness.

After this introduction, Section II presents the related work. Then, the preliminaries are introduced in Section III. Sections IV and V describe the offline training methodology. Section VI describes the simulated and real experiments, including the task parameter derivation from point clouds. Finally, the performance and future directions are discussed in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORK

Obstacle avoidance is a fundamental challenge in robotic motion planning and is approached with various methods [15]. The RRT-Connect planner [2] samples random configurations from the start and goal positions online. It is fast and probabilistically complete, however, the solutions are not optimal. The CHOMP planner [16] refines an initial path to be collision-free and optimal, requiring longer planning times.

Learning-based approaches present a promising alternative [1], leveraging offline training to reduce the computational effort online. Motion Planning Networks [4] use training data generated by optimal planners to learn to predict the next collision-free robot configuration given a point cloud and the current and goal configuration.

Other learning-based approaches encode one or multiple demonstrations as Movement Primitives (MP) [6]–[11], which provide some generalization ability by design. Further generalization capabilities are often achieved by specified task parameters, which describe how the demonstrations vary, e.g. by different goal positions, via-points or obstacle dimensions.

Previous work trains a mixture of Gaussian mixture models (GMMs) on few demonstrations to generate DMP forcing terms, achieving interpolation and extrapolation with up to two task parameters [6]. In contrast, our approach generalizes to up to three task parameters and random start and goal variations. Other methods infer task parameters from images and rely on online optimization for unseen configurations [8], whereas our approach does not require online optimization. Task parameters have also been mapped to DMP-GMM variants using neural networks to achieve multi-modal avoidance [7].

Our method similarly enables multi-modal solutions using artificially generated demonstrations, while also allowing automatic task-parameter derivation from point cloud data.

Alternatively, PI^2 can be used to improve the quality of parameterized human demonstrations by optimizing user-defined cost functions. For example, stability and acceleration penalties are used to improve the grasp quality [17]. It is also used to adapt a demonstration to new scenarios [10]. In these works, the PI^2 optimization must be run online before every new scenario. On the contrary, our work utilizes the PI^2 optimization offline to generate a dataset, allowing a NN to infer DMP forcing term parameters in real-time.

Instead of optimizing the DMP parameters, other approaches use PI^2 to optimize the parameters of potential fields for obstacle avoidance tasks [11]. This allows keeping the same parameters for similar problems. The approach is designed for obstacle avoidance with a mobile robot that considers the object dimensions in the potential field generation and an additional safety distance. In their cost function, the authors compute the similarity to the demonstration, which they compare to solutions by sampling-based motion planners. Our contribution can be applied for robot end-effectors of varying sizes in 3D space and also compares to sampling-based motion planners, but regarding planning and execution times, trajectory lengths and smoothness.

PI^2 can also be used to perturb the shape of a linear min-jerk demonstration guided by a cost function that considers task-related obstacle parameters (e.g. height) [18]. At each PI^2 iteration, the incremental distortion of the trajectories corresponds to a gradual increase in the task parameters, thereby automatically generating samples for training an action policy that maps task parameters to the forcing-term parameters of a DMP trajectory generator.

Also off-policy RL agents can be combined with DMPs for obstacle avoidance and stacking tasks [9], collecting human demonstrations for the replay buffer. The agent learns to estimate the DMP forcing term each time step, given the end-effector position and velocity, as well as the distance to the obstacle and the DMP phase variable. While this approach improves generalization, it poses challenges to the stability of the DMP model and requires hundreds of human demonstrations.

Our contribution follows the same paradigm as in [18] to efficiently generate collision-free trajectories, because it enables the efficient generation of collision-free trajectories for a rich set of obstacle configurations without the need for collecting human demonstrations. We define a new set of continuous task parameters that are automatically detected from a point cloud, rather than handcrafted, which permits generating multi-modal solutions using offsets that ensure obstacle avoidance for different end-effector dimensions and obstacle shapes. We improve the cost function formulations to be generalizable to varying applications, include cost functions that penalize initial acceleration and jerk to improve motion smoothness and adopt the more robust DMP formulation of [13]. To validate our contributions, we carry out a comprehensive experimental evaluation, including four different and more complex scenarios, a comparison with RRT-Connect and CHOMP, and real-robot experiments.

III. PRELIMINARIES

A. Task Parameterization

The task parameters $\mathcal{T} = [s_1, \dots, s_n]$ compactly describe different obstacle sizes and locations. Fig. 1 shows four example models \mathcal{M} (*1P-2D*, *3P-2D*, *2P-2D*, *3P-3D*). The simple *1P-2D* uses one task parameter for a symmetric obstacle between the start and goal. In contrast, the more complex *3P-2D* model can capture the size and location of the obstacle more precisely, enabling shorter avoidance trajectories. This model serves as the main example in this work. The other two models are designed for more specific problems. The *2P-2D* model considers an obstacle that surrounds the goal (insertion). The *3P-3D* model creates 3D trajectories for a specific avoidance problem with two walls and a gap. New models for other applications can be created by following the methodology explained in this work.

B. Dynamic Movement Primitives

DMPs [12] model each degree of freedom as a spring-damper system with a learnable forcing term $f(\phi)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau \dot{v} &= K(g - x) - Dv + (g - x_0)f(\phi) \\ \tau \dot{x} &= v, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where τ is a temporal scaling factor, x_0 and x are the initial and current positions, v the current velocity and g the goal position. The spring and damping constants $K = 25$ and $D = 2\sqrt{K}$ make the system critically damped. The phase variable $\phi \in (0, 1]$ decays exponentially, $\tau \dot{\phi} = -\alpha\phi$, with a constant α . Defining $f(\phi)$ as a normalized linear combination of basis functions allows reshaping the linear behavior arbitrarily and imitating a demonstrated trajectory. Then, $f(\phi)$ is approximated with N Gaussian radial basis functions $\psi_i(\phi)$,

$$f(\phi) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \theta_i \psi_i(\phi)}{\sum_{i=1}^N \psi_i(\phi)} \phi, \text{ with } \psi_i(\phi) = \exp(-h_i(\phi - c_i)^2), \quad (2)$$

where θ_i are the *DMP parameters* or *forcing term parameters*, which are placed at centers c_i with widths h_i along the trajectory with duration T ,

$$c_i = \exp\left(-\alpha \frac{iT}{N}\right), \quad h_i = \frac{\tilde{h}}{(c_{i+1} - c_i)^2}, \quad h_N = h_{N-1}, \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{h} = 0.5$ defines the overlap of the basis functions. The initial forcing term parameters can be derived from a demonstrated trajectory by solving Equation (2). For d -dimensional motion, one DMP per dimension is used sharing the phase ϕ . The formulation

$$\begin{aligned} \tau \dot{\mathbf{v}} &= \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{x}_0)\phi + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{f}(\phi), \\ \tau \dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{v}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

preserves the trajectory shape under arbitrary scalings and rotations, where $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{g}, \mathbf{f}(\phi) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ are diagonal matrices.

To initialize the trajectory, a one-dimensional demonstration $\mathbf{x}_D(t)$ is artificially generated by a fifth-order polynomial that starts and ends with zero velocity, resulting in a linear

minimum jerk trajectory, modeled to imitate human voluntary arm movements [19]. This demonstration is applied to the primary axis \mathbf{e}_1 of a three-dimensional DMP,

$$\mathbf{e}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{x}_0}{L}, \quad (5)$$

where $L = \|\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{x}_0\|$ and the remaining basis vectors $\mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3$ are orthogonal to \mathbf{e}_1 to span the 3D Cartesian space.

Moreover, this representation allows generating multi-modal 2D trajectories by rotating the learned forcing term around the primary axis \mathbf{e}_1 using an angle β ,

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_{new} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathbf{e}_1} \\ \cos(\beta)\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathbf{e}_2} \\ \sin(\beta)\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathbf{e}_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

More details on the DMP formulation and implementation are provided in [13].

C. Policy Improvement with Path Integrals

PI² [14] is a model-free, policy-based RL algorithm that optimizes the DMP parameters θ_i^j at each iteration j , creating $q = 1, \dots, Q$ perturbed policies,

$$\theta_{i,q}^{j+1} = \theta_i^j + \epsilon_{i,q}^j, \quad \epsilon_{i,q}^j \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i^2). \quad (7)$$

Each policy is evaluated by a trajectory-level cost $S(\theta_{i,q}^j)$ (discussed in Section IV) and assigned an importance weight $W(\theta_{i,q}^j)$,

$$W(\theta_{i,q}^j) = \exp\left(-\gamma \frac{S(\theta_{i,q}^j) - \min S(\theta_i^j)}{\max S(\theta_i^j) - \min S(\theta_i^j)}\right), \quad (8)$$

The updated DMP parameters are the normalized, weighted average of all Q samples,

$$\theta_i^{j+1} = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^Q W(\theta_{i,q}^j) \theta_{i,q}^j}{\sum_{q=1}^Q W(\theta_{i,q}^j)}. \quad (9)$$

This simplified PI² formulation improves the performance and accelerates convergence by sampling $\epsilon_{i,q}^j$ only once, and delaying the policy update until after the last time step, using the accumulated cost [20]. We refer below to the set of DMP parameters θ_i as the vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

Sampling all ϵ_i from the same distribution results in stronger trajectory shape perturbations in the beginning of the trajectory, due to the exponentially decaying phase ϕ . To encourage a symmetric shape perturbation, in this work, the exploration noise ϵ_i is sampled from a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i^2)$, where

$$\sigma_i^2 = (\exp(\hat{\sigma}_i) - 1)^2 \quad (10)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_i = \sigma^- + (\sigma^+ - \sigma^-) \left(\frac{i}{N-1}\right), \quad (11)$$

and σ^-, σ^+ are two empirically chosen hyper-parameters that create an exponential growth of σ_i^2 .

Fig. 2. PI² cost function effects: Continuous S_{shape} cost function, a) s_1 as the distance from the center, and b-c) s_1 as the trajectory height between p_1 and p_2 . S_{scope} constrains the trajectory to the left in b) and within a gap in c). Also in c), task parameter s_2 is defined by a constant ratio s_1/s_2 .

IV. DATA GENERATION WITH PI²

The PI² optimization generates a training dataset \mathcal{D} for a task that can be parameterized by $\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. A single PI² optimization run generates data along one continuous dimension s_1 . This is shown in Fig. 1 for all four examples where the optimization starts with the linear demonstration, which develops continuously along one dimension (black-to-blue gradient). More discrete task dimensions can be added by performing one PI² optimization run for each discretized combination of parameters. This scales exponentially with each discretized dimension [8]. As an alternative, we show for the $3P-2D$ model that the dataset can be generated from randomly initialized values.

The PI² optimization is driven by a cost S that is computed as the sum of weighted individual cost terms, defined for a specific task. In this work, we use four different types of cost functions: i) S_{shape} to continuously reshape the trajectory, ii) S_{scope} to constrain the reshaping process to desired areas, iii) $S_{acc,0}$ to penalize the initial acceleration and iv) S_{jerk} to penalize the overall jerk. Different scaling factors C allow prioritizing the influence of a cost function term. The cost S_{shape} continuously decreases, creating optimal trajectories for different scenarios,

$$S_{shape} = -C_{shape} \min_{t \in \mathcal{I}_{shape}} u(t), \quad (12)$$

where $C_{shape} = 1$ throughout this work, the time set $\mathcal{I}_{shape} \subset [0, T]$ denote the set of time instants on which the cost is evaluated and $u(t)$ is a one dimensional vector of positions or distances. Fig. 2 illustrates three examples that keep decreasing over time until a target value S_{shape}^* is reached, which stops the optimization. In a), S_{shape} is defined as a circle with maximum radius that fits inside the whole trajectory, placed at the center point. This is used for the $1P-2D$ model. In Fig. 2 b), S_{shape} is defined as the minimum value of x_{e_2} in the time interval $\mathcal{I}_{shape} = [t_1, t_2]$, where t_1 and t_2 are the times at which the trajectory reaches the positions p_1 and p_2 along the direction e_1 , respectively. This function is used for the $3P-2D$ and $2P-2D$ models, as well as for the third dimension (x_{e_3}) of the $3P-3D$ model. A more complex scenario is shown in c), where the x_{e_2} value of the trajectory is evaluated in two sections, defined by four points (p_1, \dots, p_4), with $\mathcal{I}_{shape} = [t_1, t_2] \cup [t_3, t_4]$, representing two trajectory peaks with a constant height ratio s_1/s_2 . This function is used for the second dimension of the $3P-3D$ model.

The second type of cost function is used to restrain the trajectory to pass barriers that are defined by S_{scope} as

$$S_{scope} = -C_{scope} \int_{t \in \mathcal{I}_{scope}} \min(0, \eta(\nu(t) - \hat{\nu}) + m) dt, \quad (13)$$

where $C_{scope} = 1$ unless specified differently, $\nu(t)$ is a one-dimensional vector of positions, $\hat{\nu}$ defines a reference that $\nu(t)$ is compared to, considering an offset m , and $\eta \in \{-1, 1\}$ defines either an upper or lower bound. The effect can be seen in Fig. 2b, where $\nu(t) = x_{e_1}(t)$, $\hat{\nu} = 0$, $m = 0.02L$, $\eta = 1$ and $\mathcal{I}_{scope} = [0, T]$. Again, c) shows a more complex scenario with two instances of S_{scope} to constrain the trajectory between p_5 and p_6 ($\mathcal{I}_{scope} = [t_5, t_6]$) with an upper ($\eta = -1$) and lower ($\eta = 1$) bound, where $\nu(t) = x_{e_2}(t)$, $\hat{\nu} = 0.02L$ and $m = 0.007L$.

The optimization with PI² also allows considering features other than the trajectory positions. Particularly within collaborative robotics, the psychological safety of humans can be improved by avoiding sudden accelerations of the robot [21]. To this end, the two following cost functions penalize the initial acceleration and overall jerk. The cost for the initial acceleration $S_{acc,0}$ is defined as

$$S_{acc,0} = C_{acc,0} \|\ddot{\mathbf{x}}(0)\|_1, \quad (14)$$

where $\ddot{\mathbf{x}}(0)$ is the initial acceleration of a multi-dimensional trajectory $\mathbf{x}(t)$. The cost for the overall jerk S_{jerk} is defined as

$$S_{jerk} = C_{jerk} \sqrt{\int_{t=0}^T \|\ddot{\mathbf{x}}(t)\|_2^2 dt}, \quad (15)$$

where $C_{acc,0} = 0.01$ and $C_{jerk} = 0.05$ are scaling constants empirically determined to ensure that S_{shape} has priority, as S_{shape} encourages longer trajectories leading to larger acceleration and jerk. Although DMP and cost functions are defined in continuous time, in practice, the DMPs are rolled out using a fixed integration step $\Delta t = 0.01$ and costs are evaluated on the resulting discrete trajectories.

As an example, five cost functions are deployed for the $3P-2D$ model. The S_{shape} (12) features $u(t) = x_{e_2}(t)$, $t \in [t_1, t_2]$, the x_{e_2} components of the trajectory between p_1 and p_2 . At the beginning of each PI² optimization, p_1 and p_2 are sampled randomly within $[0.03L, 0.97L]$, with the condition $p_2 \geq p_1$. Additionally, three S_{scope} cost functions (13) constrain the trajectory: one prevents collisions with the ground by penalizing $x_{e_2} < 0$, while the other two bound the motion along x_{e_1} within $[0, L]$ using a margin $m = 0.033L$ (similar to Fig. 2b, but on both sides). The optimization target is set to $S_{shape}^* = -L$. This can be set arbitrarily large, but will increase optimization time and dataset size. The data generation of the 50 PI² optimization runs take 40 minutes. An overview of the data generation compared to the other models is shown in Table I.

V. NEURAL NETWORK TRAINING AND TESTING

A single PI² optimization run generates a unique trajectory at each step j defined by $S_{shape,j}$. This trajectory is labeled by the corresponding forcing term parameters θ_j . When reaching the target S_{shape}^* , $J = j^*$ trajectories can be added to the dataset \mathcal{D} . In this manner, a single optimization run creates

TABLE I
MODEL VARIATIONS

Model	1P-2D	3P-2D	2P-2D	3P-3D
PI² Data Generation				
Size of θ (N)	10	10	20	60
σ^- / σ^+	.0003 / .05	.0007 / .13	.006 / .1	.0015 / .06
PI ² runs	1	50	5	30
S_{shape} in Fig. 2	a	b	b	b, c
S_{scope}	1 \times	3 \times	2 \times	5 \times
$S_{acc,0}, S_{jerk}$	✓	✓	✓	✗
Target S_{shape}^*	-0.47L	-L	-0.33L	-0.33L
Computation time	1m27s	40m15s	17m27s	2h48m
Neural Network Training				
Training data size	199	5.1k	1.0k	7.4k
Input size n	1	3	2	3
Hidden layer size	1028	256 \times 512	256 \times 512	256 \times 512
Output size	20	20	40	180
Computation time	1s	11s	4s	39s

the whole dataset for one-dimensional task parameter vector $\mathcal{T} = [s_1]$, where $s_1 = -S_{shape}$. More dimensional task parameter spaces will get additional inputs based on s_2 and s_3 that distinguish different PI² optimization runs. In these cases, the dataset is generated by drawing an equal number of samples from each optimization run using the minimum number of completion steps J_{min} across all runs. When a run has more steps than J_{min} , samples are drawn uniformly to maintain balance. The NN architecture consists of one or two fully connected hidden layers, the training is performed with the *Adam* optimizer and a learning rate of 0.0005 using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss. The training is implemented with PyTorch [22] and the trained model is saved as a scripted model. An overview of the NN training for all the models is shown in Table I.

Since the NN approximates optimal PI² trajectories, a small optimality gap is unavoidable. Performance is therefore evaluated using the s_1 -error on 1000 randomly generated task parameters (evaluation time < 30 s). As $s_1 = -S_{shape}$ directly parameterizes the optimal PI² avoidance trajectory, the s_1 -error quantifies deviation from the optimum. For obstacle avoidance applications, positive errors lead to conservative but safe trajectories, whereas negative errors may cause collisions. Hence, an offset o is introduced and incrementally increased until no negative errors occur.

Using the 3P-2D model example, fifty PI² optimization runs generate 5.1k trajectories for the NN using two hidden layers with 256 and 512 nodes. The training is performed for 100 epochs within 11 s. Without an offset, the s_1 -error lies in $[-0.031L, 0.032L]$. Applying $o = 0.02L$ shifts the error range to $[0.000L, 0.068L]$. The offset is applied as $s_1 + o$, $s_2 - o$, $s_3 + o$ to increase the avoidance space. Additionally, 100 optimal trajectories from 20 independent PI² runs (within the training range but excluded from the training dataset) are compared to NN predictions using identical cost terms. The resulting s_1 -error lies in $[-0.021L, 0.018L]$. Boundary violations defined by S_{scope} are limited to $0.002L$ (bottom) and $0.019L$ (sides). The combined acceleration and jerk costs deviate within $[-16.3\%, 33.4\%]$. These results confirm that the NN reproduces near-optimal trajectories.

A 2D avoidance example illustrates the model’s ability to

Fig. 3. 2D avoidance example using the 3P-2D model with different obstacles (blue): a) near-optimal, smooth trajectories for random start and goal initialization, b) bi-modal solutions, c) considering four different obstacle dimensions.

create smooth near-optimal trajectories for four different start-goal pairs that are randomly sampled on either side of an ellipsoidal obstacle, initialized with a trajectory duration of one second (Fig. 3a). In Fig. 3b, instead of only choosing the shortest path, a second solution is shown, avoiding three obstacles to both sides. The flexibility of setting different offsets can also be used for different end-effector or mobile robot dimensions w , e.g. $s_1 + w_{e_2}$, $s_2 - 0.5w_{e_1}$ and $s_3 + 0.5w_{e_1}$. In Fig. 3c, trajectory solutions with different end-effector dimensions are presented.

VI. EXPERIMENTS

The effectiveness of the proposed approach is presented in four 3D experiments with a UR5e manipulator and realsense camera in simulation using ROS 2 Humble and Gazebo 11 Classic. We carry out experiments in a variety of tasks: a pick-and-drop, an insertion, and a 3D avoidance experiment that are inspired by [8], as well as a stacking experiment (see Fig. 1). Finally, the 3P-2D model is applied in a real robot experiment.

The initial DMP parameters are obtained from a single demonstration $\mathbf{x}_D(t)$. The length L of $\mathbf{x}_D(t)$ is used to scale the DMP parameters θ to maintain the same trajectory shape. The current end-effector position is sent to the detection node that detects the goal position and the task parameters (Fig. 1). The NN model returns the respective θ that are set in the DMP and allows generating a collision-free Cartesian trajectory. This trajectory is translated into a joint trajectory using inverse kinematics (IK) (via MoveIt [23] or the Kinenik library¹), and sent to the robot using a ROS 2 joint trajectory action.

To perform the experiments automatically in different scenarios, task parameters and goal positions are derived directly from point cloud data using Open3D [24]. To this end, the point cloud data is first preprocessed, reducing the point cloud size via downsampling and transforming it into world coordinates. In the example with the 3P-2D model, obstacle and goal object are isolated by removing points belonging to the robot and the floor. The goal position is derived using 2D density-based clustering to find the goal object. To capture the position and dimensions of the obstacle, three task parameters must be derived. Fig. 4b shows an example in a rotated coordinate frame with the preliminary

¹<https://gitioc.upc.edu/robots/kinenik>

Fig. 4. Pick-and-Drop experiment: a-b) task parameter derivation with $3P-2D$, and c) experiment setup and comparison to $1P-2D$ and baselines.

task parameters $\hat{\mathcal{T}} = [\hat{s}_1, \hat{s}_2, \hat{s}_3]$ that create a collision-free trajectory for a point mass. The final task parameters \mathcal{T} consider the end-effector dimensions w as shown previously in Fig. 3c. However, in this 3D experiment, three solutions for s_1 are considered by finding the points with the maximum e_2 (right) and e_3 (up) values as well as the minimum e_2 (left) value, creating multi-modal solutions.

A. Pick-and-Drop

In this experiment, the $1P-2D$ and $3P-2D$ models are compared with each other and with three baselines. The *Linear* baseline consists of three linear segments, with intermediate waypoints provided by the $3P-2D$ detection. Our models and the *Linear* baseline create trajectories in Cartesian space using by default only the shortest solution: $\min([s_1^{\text{left}}, s_1^{\text{right}}, s_1^{\text{up}}])$. If the resulting trajectory is infeasible, the run is considered a failure. Additionally, we evaluate a Multi-Modal (MM) strategy for the $3P-2D$ model, that generates a trajectory in the direction of the alternative solutions, if the shortest solution fails. The other two baselines plan trajectories in joint space using RRT-Connect [2] and CHOMP [16], implemented in MoveIt [23]. *CHOMP* is initialized with a linear trajectory and a maximum of 200 iterations. The Cartesian trajectories are also executed via MoveIt to consider the same workspace and joint acceleration constraints.

The pick-and-drop experiment requires picking and carrying a cube to the other side of an obstacle and into a cup (Fig. 4a). The position of the cube and the cup are sampled randomly inside two workspaces with dimensions 0.4×0.4 m on opposite sides of the obstacle (see example in Fig. 4c). The obstacle is a configuration of up to 20 blocks, centered at $x = 0.0$ m, $y = 0.5$ m. For the comparison, 50 random configurations are sampled. Execution, planning, and detection times, trajectory length, jerk, and success rate are evaluated (Table II). *RRT* solves all feasible cases but has the longest execution times and trajectories. *CHOMP* achieves short execution times and joint trajectories but requires long planning times. The *Linear* method plans fastest and yields short Cartesian paths but exhibits the highest jerk. Our DMP-based methods are significantly smoother than *Linear* and plan much faster than *CHOMP*, at the cost of slightly longer execution due to joint acceleration limits. The $1P-2D$ has the worst success rate. The MM strategy increases the success rate for the $3P-2D$ model, but also the execution and planning times, as more sub-optimal trajectories are executed and two or three iterations are required for the runs where $3P-2D$ fails initially. In total, the DMP-based models and CHOMP are the fastest in terms of

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON (MEAN \pm STD).

	$1P-2D$	$3P-2D$	$3P-2D_{MM}$	<i>CHOMP</i>	<i>Linear</i>	<i>RRT</i>
ET \downarrow	$3.6 \pm .71$	$3.2 \pm .60$	$3.3 \pm .82$	$2.3 \pm .34$	$3.8 \pm .54$	7.4 ± 3.0
DT \downarrow	$.09 \pm .01$	$.09 \pm .01$	$.08 \pm .01$	$.08 \pm .01$	$.09 \pm .01$	$.09 \pm .01$
PT \downarrow	$.06 \pm .01$	$.06 \pm .01$	$.08 \pm .05$	$.98 \pm .12$	$.03 \pm .01$	$.27 \pm .33$
CL \downarrow	$.88 \pm .14$	$.80 \pm .13$	$.82 \pm .15$	$.86 \pm .17$	$.79 \pm .13$	$1.6 \pm .78$
JL \downarrow	$2.8 \pm .69$	$2.6 \pm .65$	$2.8 \pm .82$	$1.9 \pm .31$	$2.5 \pm .61$	9.1 ± 4.0
JJ \downarrow	$1.2 \pm .15$	$1.4 \pm .25$	$1.3 \pm .28$	$1.1 \pm .37$	$1.9 \pm .28$	$.61 \pm .28$
MJ \downarrow	8.6 ± 2.4	9.5 ± 2.8	9.8 ± 2.8	12.8 ± 1.6	13.6 ± 1.3	11.8 ± 3.3
SR \uparrow	73.5	87.8	98.0	93.9	83.7	100

ET: Execution Time [s]; DT: Detection Time [s]; PT: Planning Time [s]; CL: Cartesian trajectory Length [m]; JL: Joint trajectory Length [rad]; JJ: Joint Jerk [rad/s³]; MJ: Maximum joint Jerk [rad/s³]; SR: Success Rate [%]. The arrows indicate if higher or lower values represent a better performance.

Fig. 5. Comparison of our $1P-2D$ and $3P-2D$ models to three baselines: a) Computation time for detection and planning and execution time. b) Detailed contributions to computation time for detection and planning.

combined computation times for detection and planning, and execution times, considering only runs in which they found a feasible solution, indicated in bold in Fig. 5a. To quantify the impact of the success rate, we introduce a *RRT* fallback when one of the methods does not find a feasible trajectory, and add the planning times for the failed attempts and the accumulated mean *RRT* time. The outlined block with dashed lines shows the sum of execution, detection and planning times for all runs, including the *RRT* fallbacks. Now, the $3P-2D_{MM}$ method performs best, followed by *CHOMP* and $3P-2D$. Due to short planning times, DMP failures are inexpensive and allow efficient fallback.

In Fig. 5b, the detailed detection and planning operations are listed, including their respective computation times, showing that the robot configuration sampling of the *CHOMP* and *RRT* planners takes the most time, as well as sampling the Cartesian trajectory collision checks. On the other hand, the NN inference and the linear trajectory generation contribute marginally. The detection times are similar for all methods. The *RRT* does not require computing the obstacle parameters, which is a marginal effort. The initial downsampling of the point cloud takes the most time in the detection part.

B. Stacking, Insertion and 3D Avoidance

To demonstrate scalability and transferability, three additional experiments were conducted. **Stacking:** Two sequential pick-and-place operations stack two cubes onto a third while avoiding obstacles. Three trajectories are generated

using the $3P-2D$ model from the pick-and-drop experiment. Fig. 1 shows the initial point cloud, the generated trajectories, and a simulation snapshot before placing the second cube. In contrast to pick-and-drop, precise stacking requires close goal approach and a varying z goal coordinate. Five stacks with different initial cube configurations were successfully executed. **Insertion:** A peg is inserted into a box with a hole that allows 0.005 m insertion tolerance, requiring a precise vertical descent. The $2P-2D$ model is trained using S_{scope} with an upper bound close to the goal, as well as a S_{shape} where p_2 is constant and close to the goal. Two trajectories are generated, one to the pick location of the peg and another one to the insertion location of the hole. Five PP optimizations with different p_1 locations are performed to create the dataset. All 20 runs succeed, with only minor initial collisions in two cases between peg and box at the beginning of the insertion process. **3D avoidance:** The $3P-3D$ model is trained to generate a 3D trajectory that avoids two outer walls of varying heights and, in between, passing through a gap with varying y position and 0.02 m tolerance. Unlike the other experiments, this one has constant start and goal positions. The three tasks parameters describe the heights of the walls (s_1, s_2) and the position of the gap (s_3). In 20 experiment runs with random gap location and the same wall configurations as in the training, all but one are successful. The one failed experiment collided inside the gap. This shows the challenge with gaps as no offset can be set to improve the performance. The basis function overlap could be reduced by increasing \hat{h} (3) allowing trajectories with sharper turns. We would like to note that configuring sampling-based planners (e.g., RRT and CHOMP) in MoveIt to satisfy hard 3D constraints, such as fixed end-effector orientation and motion through gaps, is impractical, whereas our approach encodes these constraints with a few parameters, enabling efficient generation of feasible trajectories. More details about these models are available online².

C. Real Robot Experiments

We evaluate the transferability of the $3P-2D$ model with one UR5 arm of a bimanual mobile manipulator and an external rc_visard stereo camera (Fig. 6). Avoidance experiments are conducted without a hand and for the pick-and-drop experiment an Allegro hand is used. The camera on the mobile manipulator is used to calibrate the pose of the rc_visard by detecting the same markers on a table. A private 5G network is used to communicate the generated collision-free trajectory to the robot controller. Starting with the robot end-effector on one side of an obstacle, the goal object is placed on the other side of the obstacle, such that it is reachable and a collision-free trajectory exists. Subsequently, the point cloud areas of the goal object and the obstacle are processed on the edge computer, receiving the point cloud directly from the camera. The collision-free Cartesian trajectory is computed and interpolated based on a desired execution duration, and an IK service on the robot is called via 5G to convert it into a joint trajectory. Finally, the joint trajectory is sent to the robot controller and executed. There are two main differences compared to the simulated experiment. First, the

Fig. 6. Real robot example with three snapshots of a pick-and-drop experiment and the corresponding point cloud image with the generated DMP trajectory (green line): a) the corresponding Cartesian velocity and acceleration, b) the smoothed measured joint velocities and accelerations.

UR5 is mounted on the robot instead of on the ground. The model generates the same Cartesian trajectory, but the joint trajectories are different. This shows that the approach is model-free and can be used with any robot manipulator. Secondly, besides boxes and a cup, various household objects are used as obstacles and three goal objects of different heights are utilized. This shows that any object can be avoided or serve as goal object as long as the camera can create a point cloud of it. Without the Allegro hand, 27 obstacle-avoidance trials were conducted using cardboard boxes and YCB food and kitchen items [25]. Assuming executability of the generated Cartesian trajectories, 26 trials succeeded and one failed due to an arm collision, motivating whole-body collision checking as in the simulated pick-and-drop experiment (Sec. VI-A). With the Allegro hand, nine avoidance trajectories were generated, including five pick-and-drop operations in two containers and on one can. All avoidance trajectories succeeded, but one of the two drop actions on the can failed due to combined inaccuracies in goal detection and grasping/releasing. Two main observations arise from the real-robot experiments: (i) trajectory execution is smooth (Fig. 6), as shown by Cartesian end-effector and joint velocity/acceleration profiles, although joint-space smoothness is not guaranteed near singularities, requiring joint acceleration limits, and (ii) the effect of the grasped object on the collision space is difficult to detect automatically but is important for near-optimal trajectories, and is partially handled by manually adjusting the trajectory shape via the offset o .

VII. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

We identify some limitations of the approach and directions for future work. **Error scaling:** DMP scaling improves generalization but also amplifies errors, complicating tasks with tight tolerances, like insertion or gap navigating. Future work could exploit the DMP's dynamic adaptation ability to mitigate this issue. **Model complexity:** Four compact models were presented in this work, each requiring data generation, learning and task parameter derivation. The models generalize across different object configurations as long as the avoidance

²<https://github.com/DominikUrbaniak/obst-avoid-dmp-pi2>

Fig. 7. Extrapolation ability of 3P-2D for each of the three task parameter.

problem can be characterized by the model’s task parameters. However, this reliance on task parameters limits scalability in less structured scenes. In multi-obstacle scenarios, the current derivation from point clouds approximates all obstacles as a single bounding box, which may lead to overly conservative trajectories. Clutter or nonconvex obstacles could lead to task parameters outside the training range. In such extrapolation cases, the model accuracy decreases (Fig. 7). If the required avoidance maneuver is not represented by the trained trajectory distribution, the model fails systematically and a new model with adapted cost functions and training data is required. Alternatively, a higher-level decision-making framework could dynamically select, adapt, and compose trajectories from multiple avoidance models to improve generalization to new and more complex scenarios.

Inverse kinematics (IK): Our models generate Cartesian-space trajectories for collision avoidance but do not guarantee feasibility on a specific robot manipulator. To address this, we plan to delegate IK feasibility checking to the higher-level decision maker, which considers kinematically feasible model parameters during model selection and composition. This preserves model efficiency and transferability across robotic platforms without increasing model complexity or requiring retraining.

Engineering effort: While the modular design ensures computational efficiency, interpretability and reuse of components, it shifts complexity toward system engineering. For each model, task parameters must be defined, cost functions designed, training data generated, and scene-to-parameter mappings constructed. Offsets are currently added to address approximation errors, sensor noise and end-effector dimensions. All of these offsets can be accumulated and only make the avoidance trajectories more conservative. Learning the task parameter derivation directly from point clouds could reduce manual tuning and improve optimality in multi-obstacle scenarios.

VIII. CONCLUSION

We presented a method that generates collision-free trajectories online within 0.2 s, after two minutes to less than three hours of offline training, based on a single artificially-generated demonstration and a general cost function formulation that enables data generation via PI². The application to four different scenarios was presented, showing generalization to varying goal locations and obstacle types and sizes. Its smooth and near-optimal trajectories are executed on average at least 16% faster than the *Linear* and *RRT-Connect* baselines and as fast as the *CHOMP* baseline under identical joint acceleration limits, offering additional seamless multi-modal solutions and a favorable combination with probabilistic complete planners due to small overhead planning times in

failure cases. The required task parameters are automatically derived from a point cloud, which was shown in simulated and real experiments.

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